

COMPASS

Guidelines for compound extremes modelling in current and future climates

Deliverable 1.1

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Deliverable 1.1 - Guidelines for compound extremes modelling in current and future climates

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Executive summary

The overarching goal of the COMPASS project is to develop a harmonised methodological framework for climate and impact attribution of various complex extremes that includes compound, sequences and cascading hazard events. This report, deliverable D1.1, presents an inventory of datasets and introduces modelling workflows for characterizing compound extremes in current and future climates. It contributes to the COMPASS project's objective of improving hazard modelling with sufficient accuracy at the local scale and to the Work Package 1 objective of developing a flexible hazard modelling approach for compound extremes. This report is a foundational step in guiding modelling efforts, supporting future work in specific hazard scenarios, and linking to other deliverables, such as D2.1 from Work Package 2, which more specifically addresses climate attribution methods and datasets. Deliverable 1.1 will be updated throughout the project, leading to deliverable D1.2 at the end of the project, which will integrate lessons learned from the hazard modelling process and integrated into the guidelines.

This report focuses on the following compound extreme events: compound pluvial, fluvial and coastal flooding either from tropical cyclones or from winter storms, compound coastal flooding and windstorms from extra-tropical cyclones, hydrological drought and saltwater intrusion and compound heatwaves with droughts. We present the hazard modelling workflows, i.e. the modelling chains, that will be applied to model each compound event types along with possible global or continental datasets that can be used. We also list specific requirements needed for each Use Case (UC), i.e. a selected recent event from each compound event type. The UC cover a wide variety of compound hazards, over many different geographical areas, where local or regional data availability differs in terms of spatial and temporal coverage.

Compound extremes have complex spatiotemporal dynamics that must be accurately captured to model their impacts accurately. We identify specific points of attention of importance and recommendations applicable to all UCs for the compound hazard modelling, mainly regarding the uncertainties introduced by the modelling chain and the spatial and temporal resolution of the input datasets. The quality and resolution of the input datasets can significantly affect the accuracy of modelled hazard and thus the ability to make robust attribution statements. Some recommendations have already been included in the workflows, for example by incorporating statistical downscaling and/or dynamical downscaling of climate drivers. Similarly, validation of the workflow will be performed when possible and uncertainties will be quantified along the modelling chain by testing different input datasets. The updated version of this report will expand and consolidate the guidelines based on the outcomes of the UC hazard modelling.

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1. Introduction

The modelling of compound extremes requires various datasets, ranging from meteorological data derived from climate models or reanalysis datasets to land cover or elevation data derived from satellites. The modelling of compound extremes requires specific workflows, or modelling chains, to accurately model the many processes involved during such event. This is complicated by the fact that compound events often have important spatiotemporal dynamics that need to be modelled to fully capture their impacts. The availability and quality of forcing and static datasets further influence the accuracy of the modelled hazards. It is therefore important to have an overview of these sources of uncertainties and how they influence modelling efforts. For example, the temporal and spatial resolution of these datasets is important to limit uncertainties and allow for robust attribution statements. Uncertainties can be large while high accuracy is required to be able to provide actionable information.

This deliverable, D1.1, provides an inventory of datasets and introduces modelling workflows that can be used for the characterization of compound extremes in current and future climates. By doing so, it contributes to one of COMPASS specific objectives (SO) to *“Improve hazard modelling of compound extremes in current and future climates with sufficient accuracy at local scale”*. COMPASS focusses on (the combinations of) rainfall, coastal flood, tropical cyclones, windstorms, wildfires, heatwaves, drought and saltwater intrusion. The goal of Work Package 1 is to create a flexible global to local approach for hazard modelling that uses dynamic and statistical downscaling to improve the local accuracy of hazard data, leveraging existing tools, models, and climate data. This deliverable is a first step in that direction and aims to provide guidance for modelling activities to be carried out during the project. It also underlies specific hazard modelling that needs to be carried out for the Use Cases (UC) in Work Package 4. It is closely linked to D2.1 that presents the best available methods and climate datasets for impact attribution. This report will be updated throughout the project and result in a final report to be issued as deliverable D1.2 that will reflect all the details and lessons learned from the hazard modelling of the selected compound extremes.

1.1. Terminology

The terms *“compound extremes”* and *“compound events”* are used interchangeably and used as a general term to encompass complex spatiotemporal dynamics from weather-driven hazards. Zscheischler et al. (2020) define four main types of compound events (i.e. preconditioned, multivariate, spatially compounding and temporally compounding) based on the spatial and temporal characteristics. However, some compound events can fall under many types, as exemplified by tropical and extratropical cyclones. Tropical cyclones (TC) involve simultaneous flood drivers such as rainfall, wind, storm surges (multivariate event). TC-induced flooding can be further influenced depending on the saturation of the soil (preconditioned), or by rainfall events and TC events that have occurred (temporally compounding). A TC can also impact multiple regions over the course of a few days (spatially compounding). Hence *compound extremes* are therefore used as an umbrella term to not only include recent definitions of compound weather and climate events (Zscheischler et al., 2020), but also consecutive events (de Ruiter et al., 2020), sequences and cascading events (Gill & Malamud, 2014) and multiform events (Kruczkiewicz et al., 2022).

The impacts of a compound event result from the spatiotemporal dynamics of the **hazard** drivers combined with the **exposure**, defined as the assets or people exposed to that hazard event, and the **vulnerability**, defined as the social, economic, and environmental dimensions that describe the ability of the exposed elements to withstand the impact of an event (Jongman et al., 2015; Kron, 2005; UNDRR, 2017). Hazard is defined in this project as *“a process, phenomenon or human activity that may cause loss of life, injury or other health impacts, property damage, social and economic disruption or environmental degradation. Hazards may be natural, anthropogenic or socionatural in origin”* (UNDRR, 2017). In this deliverable we use the aforementioned definition and the term hazard refers to hazard events and not to the frequency or probability distribution of the hazard, a definition often used in probabilistic risk studies.

The focus of this deliverable is on compound event *hazard* modelling. Defining hazard variables usually depends on the type of events analysed. Moreover, the hazard itself may be affected by dynamics with exposure and vulnerability. For example, an increase in paved areas (change in exposure) can increase pluvial flooding (change in hazard) through, among others, a higher runoff coefficient. This is further discussed in the section 2.3.

1.2. Use Cases

The methodological framework for the compound event hazard modelling is developed by considering different compound extreme types and hazards, summarized in Table 1-1. The focus of this deliverable is therefore on the compound extremes that will be addressed by COMPASS, which include compound river and coastal floods, hydrological droughts and saltwater intrusion, compound heatwaves with other hazards, extra-tropical cyclones leading to coastal floods and windstorms, and tropical cyclones that can lead to sequential events of compound events.

Table 1-1: Overview of the considered Use Cases (UC) for Phase I of the COMPASS project

UC no.	Spatiotemporal dynamics considered ¹	Major hazard types	Event name and date	Region
1	Multivariate	- Coastal flooding (tide, storm surge) - Wind	Extratropical cyclone - storm Xynthia (2010)	France
2a	Temporally compounding, Multivariate	- Wind - Pluvial flooding - Coastal flooding (tide, storm surge)	Winter 2013/2014	United Kingdom
2b	Temporally compounding, Multivariate	- Heatwave - Drought - Wildfires	Summer 2022	United Kingdom
3a	Multivariate, spatially and temporally compounding	- Coastal flooding (tide, storm surge, waves) - Wind - Pluvial flooding - River flooding	Tropical cyclone Idai, Kenneth and Freddy	Mozambique
3b	Multivariate	- Drought - Saltwater intrusion	2015/2016	Mozambique
4	Temporally compounding and Multivariate	- Pluvial flooding - River flooding - Coastal flooding (storm surge)	Tropical cyclone Eta and Iota	Caribbean
5	Temporally compounding and Multivariate	- Heatwave - Drought	No specific event (operational demonstrator)	Poland

¹ The categories refer to the topology of compound events as defined in Zscheischler et al. (2020)

The types of hazards considered are various flooding types (pluvial, fluvial, coastal), windstorms, heatwaves (high temperatures lasting for a certain amount of time), droughts, wildfires and saltwater intrusion. The events selected exhibit a combination of spatiotemporal dynamics and cover different regions. For the same hazard types, for example coastal flooding, the quality and availability of the data across the different UCs may be different and result in different accuracy in the hazard modelling.

1.3. Structure of this report

In section 2, we provide an overview of the important processes involved in the considered compound extremes. We introduce conceptual workflows, or modelling chains that will be applied in COMPASS, that can be used to translate climate data into hazard information and mention specific points of attention to be considered for the hazard modelling. In section 3, we provide an inventory of relevant large-scale datasets that can be used for the modelling of these hazards in current and future climates. Finally, specific requirements related to each specific UC are introduced in section 4, for example concerning specific datasets and models that will be used in the COMPASS project.

2. Workflows for compound extremes modelling

This section introduces conceptual workflows highlighting important processes and input data required for the hazard modelling of compound extremes. We mention the workflows that will be applied within the COMPASS project for the considered compound extreme hazards. We also discuss uncertainties and points of attention to consider that can impact compound event hazard modelling.

2.1. Compound extreme identification

Identifying compound events remains challenging, as there is a wide variety and diversity of spatiotemporal dynamics relevant for the making of a compound event. An analysis based on a specific event definition (see section 1.1) may neglect other important spatiotemporal dynamics that influences the hazard output variables. Compound events can stem from the occurrence of drivers, some of them not being extreme. For example, coastal flooding can be exacerbated by local pluvial events or discharge, even when they are not extreme (Couasnon et al., 2020; Hendry et al., 2019). This makes traditional “top-down” approaches, based on joint threshold exceedances, not sufficient for the identification of compound events. Historical events, where impacts have been observed, often constitute a first step to explore and identify the dominant spatial and temporal scales of the event as well as the different relevant compounding hazards involved (Ben-Ari et al., 2018; Eilander et al., 2023). This is the approach put forward in the COMPASS project, through the selected Use Cases.

Based on this initial analysis, once a relevant workflow to model the compound extreme hazards has been set up, it can be reused to model similar compound extremes. For example, in a top-down approach, climate datasets can be analysed to detect similar anomalous combinations of weather and climate drivers. Applying this workflow to different locations can highlight differences or similarities in hazard, for example, due to different geography. If applied at the same location, this modelling chain applied to multiple events can inform on the frequency of the compound event, or its (change of) probability under current or future climate.

2.2. Conceptual workflows for compound hazard modelling

This section provides an overview of the key processes and data types involved in the modelling of the selected compound extremes. Most workflows are conceptual (without technical details or specific dataset names) and provide the starting point for understanding the modelling of compound extremes that results in certain output variables representing the hazard (which later can be used in impact modelling). The hazard model uses input data, either static (i.e. constant in time) or dynamic (i.e. varying in time) to generate dynamic output data. Unless specifically mentioned, we assume that the processes introduced in this section are resolved using physics-based models. Data-driven models can also be applied, if they have sufficient accuracy. In the latter case, understanding important processes and key input and output hazard variables is a starting point for the construction of a data-driven model.

2.2.1. Compound pluvial, fluvial and coastal floods

Coastal areas are exposed to multiple flood hazards, such as pluvial flooding from rainfall events, fluvial flooding from high discharge events and coastal flooding from extreme sea levels. These hazards can interact, for example when resulting from common weather systems such as storms, resulting in compound flooding.

Modelling compound flooding from fluvial, pluvial and coastal sources can be done by means of a modelling chain that consists of coupling models to account for all hazards into a flood model to obtain flood inundation maps, as shown in Figure 2-1. In this way, the output from each separate model is used to force a local compound flood model. The main advantage of this approach is that it provides details where needed, both in terms of the hazards considered and in terms of spatial resolution, going from a regional model to a local model. The dynamic input data, often from global datasets (in yellow boxes, see also section 3.1) is used as forcing to the intermediate hazard models, here the three components of compound flooding (pluvial, fluvial and coastal, green boxes) to model the relevant dynamic variables (grey boxes) for the local compound flood model (green box). This results in more detailed and accurate modelled flood dynamics (hazard output, shown in blue) than forcing the compound flood model directly from the global input datasets, a process referred to as dynamical downscaling. Each hazard model is explained next.

Figure 2-1: Hazard modelling chain for compound river, pluvial and coastal flooding.

A **hydrological model** (also referred to as a rainfall-runoff model), can be used to estimate river discharges. These models simulate various processes that occur at the earth surface based on precipitation, temperature and available energy. The processes include, among others, soil infiltration, vegetation interception, evaporation, overland flow, and snow melt. Hydrological models vary in complexity, ranging from simple lumped and conceptual models to physically based fully distributed (gridded) models that calculate processes for each grid cell. The output from these models serves as input for the flood model.

A **coastal hydrodynamic model** is used to estimate the coastal water levels, which are one of the drivers of compound flooding at the coast. Coastal water levels are influenced by the tidal conditions at the time of the extreme event, storm surge levels (increase in water levels caused by the atmospheric conditions), and mean sea level changes (averaged over set period of time, such as a month or a year). The hydrodynamic model would typically be set up for a larger area extending offshore from the coast, with a sufficient distance from the coast to accurately model surge levels generated by wind and atmospheric pressure changes during the storm. Accurate information on near-shore ocean bathymetry is an important factor affecting the overall accuracy of the coastal water level estimates. The resolution and geographic extent of the model need to be selected such that they are appropriate for the given coastal location, taking into account the steepness and geometric complexity of the bathymetry. The output of the hydrodynamic model provides timeseries of coastal water

levels at a range of output points along the coast and can be used as input to the flood model (often also combined with the wave-induced water level setup).

A **wave model** is needed to estimate the near-shore wave heights that can result in wave setup. Ocean waves originate from the disturbance of the sea surface due to sustained winds, leading to the formation of a wave field (wind sea waves). Waves with different wavelengths travel at different speeds, and as the waves propagate through the ocean, the wave field changes towards more regular and long-crested waves (also known as swells). The interaction of both sea and swell waves with different frequencies gives rise to a third wave type known as the infragravity wave. On the open ocean, infragravity waves have low wave heights, but as they approach the coast (entering into shallower waters) they will transform by shoaling. This transformation results in *wave setup*, which refers to the additional elevation of water levels from wave action by the swell and infragravity waves. In general, wave setup is larger for steeper coasts, and smaller for coasts with gentle bathymetry changes over the distance. The wave setup results in an increase in coastal water levels on top of the tide and surge water levels, and is an important component to take into account, especially in areas with steep near-shore bathymetry.

A **compound flood model** uses the modelled discharge, tide, storm surge and wave conditions from the hydrological, coastal and wave model respectively as forcing variables to simulate the resulting flood map from these combined time series. The output time series of flood depth and extent can be further analysed to understand and model the impact of the compound flood event (not covered in this report). The compound flood model usually has the finest spatial resolution, typically 30 m or less, to properly capture spatial dynamics. Local pluvial flooding is directly modelled from local rainfall forced on the area and modelled with a simple rainfall-runoff relationship, referred to as a rain-on-grid approach. When local rainfall data is not available, global rainfall datasets are used albeit their spatial and temporal resolution is too coarse to capture local and short-lived events.

Even though fluvial, pluvial and coastal flood drivers are well known as important compound flood drivers, the modelling chain presented in Figure 2-1 has seldomly been applied in compound flood hazard studies. In practice, some flood drivers are often omitted if they have a limited or no influence on flood impacts in order to simplify the workflow and reduce computational burden. For example, wave contributions are very often either included in a simplistic empirical approximation (as 20% of the significant wave height (US Army Corps of Engineers, 2002)) or fully omitted from the modelling.

2.2.2. Extra-tropical cyclones - coastal floods + windstorm

Extreme sea levels during Xynthia extra-tropical cyclone on 28 February 2010 will be primarily modelled using available European and global datasets, together with the possibility of generating counterfactual sea level back to year 1950. The modelling chain follows the approach described in Paprotny et al. (2024). As storm surge heights are only one component of extreme sea levels, the hourly total water level (L) is the combination of six components:

$$L=S+T+W+D+M+G \quad (1)$$

Where:

- S is the hourly storm surge height;
- T is the hourly tide elevation;
- W is the hourly wave run-up, assumed to be 20% of significant wave height (recommended by U.S. Army Corps of Engineers, (2002), used e.g. in Vousdoukas et al., (2016));
- D is the mean dynamic topography;
- M is the long-term variation in sea level related to climatic variation (“sea level rise”, SLR), defined as average annual difference from average sea level in year 2000;
- G is the glacial isostatic adjustment (GIA) computed from long-term historical rate of change.

For each coastal segment in the dataset, an extreme value analysis of sea level was carried out using a Generalised Pareto distribution and a peak-over-threshold approach. The analysis was carried out using maximum likelihood estimation and the 99.6th percentile threshold. This enabled deriving extreme sea level scenarios (return periods of 2, 5, 10, 20, 30, 50, 100, 200, and 500 years) for coastal inundation modelling.

The Xynthia cyclone that generated the coastal flood event later moved further inland, causing impacts through extreme winds, which will be derived directly from climate reanalysis.

Figure 2-2: Workflow of modelling coastal floods and windstorms in context of the 2010 extra-tropical cyclone Xynthia.

2.2.3. Hydrological droughts and saltwater intrusion

Hydrological drought and saltwater intrusion, also referred to as Compound Drought and Saltwater Intrusion Events (CDSEs) affects both surface and groundwater systems at the coast. Saltwater intrusion can impact both soil and water salinity through different climate-related and human-driven processes, occurring at different time scales, from days to decades, making it a particularly complex system to model. Saltwater intrusion in low-lying coastal areas can have widespread negative societal impacts by affecting freshwater resources, agriculture, fishing or surrounding aquifers.

In surface water systems, prolonged low flows reduce freshwater input to estuaries, resulting in saltwater propagating upstream. The dynamics between coastal levels (saltwater) and river discharges (freshwater), act as two opposite forces in the estuary, the former acting from downstream (sea) to upstream (river). Salinity variations are therefore not uniform across the estuary, nor across time. Other weather-related drivers, such as the wind, or anthropogenic factors such as constructions of dams upstream, can further influence fresh-saline water dynamics in estuaries. Climate change exacerbate saltwater intrusion by, among others, the occurrence of prolonged droughts and sea level rise.

In the groundwater system, groundwater extraction lowers the fresh groundwater table and promotes the intrusion of saltwater. Porous media and head differences drive salinity content in groundwater at a seasonal to decadal time scales. At the coast, sea level rise can further exacerbate saltwater intrusion from the larger hydraulic gradient between the sea and the aquifer. Low river discharge, long dry spells and increased evaporation all contribute to increase saltwater intrusion in groundwater. Here as well climate change is therefore an important driver to increasing saltwater intrusion at the coast.

To the best of our knowledge, current CDSEs studies have focused on surface water systems, modelling estuaries using a three-dimensional (3D) **hydrodynamic model**. This requires however, detailed information about bathymetry along the whole estuary. The 3D model (for e.g. Delft3D-FM) calculates salinity levels across multiple depths and width along the estuary and requires similar forcing than listed in section 2.2.1 but also salinity levels at the sea. The impacts of the drought on the discharge rates can be modelled from a **hydrological model** (see section 2.2.1). The output of this modelling chain are salinity levels in the estuary. Further postprocessing is needed to translate these levels to various impacts, for example on crop yields or drinking water.

Groundwater systems can be modelled with a groundwater model, (for e.g. MODFLOW or iMOD). Under certain simplifications using an advanced hydrological model that includes groundwater recharge (such as wflow) is an option or by coupling both the hydrological model with the groundwater model. The **groundwater model** uses various input data: recharge data, consisting of precipitation and evapotranspiration, determining infiltration to the aquifer; water systems such as lakes, rivers, sea where the hydraulic head is known; well locations and extraction rate; hydraulic properties of the aquifer like the hydraulic conductivity, determining how fast water moves vertically or horizontally through the aquifer and other soil properties that influences flow direction and gradients like topography, soil layering etc.

At this stage, it has not yet been decided whether the use case will focus on saltwater intrusion in surface water systems and/or groundwater systems. This will be updated in the next version of the document.

2.2.4. Compound Heatwaves with other hazards

The summer of 2022 was characterised by extreme temperatures across Europe and was the first time that temperatures exceeded 40 degrees Celsius in the UK. Whilst it was not the hottest summer on record in the UK (2018), or the driest summer (1995), the impacts were particularly severe due to the temporally compounding nature of prolonged low rainfall totals and sustained high temperatures. There are multiple impacts that can be modelled for a drought heatwave event including heat mortality, drought impacts and wildfires. The modelling chain for this event is shown in Figure 2-1, with two main approaches.

The first approach is a statistical one, calculating the Standard Precipitation and Evapotranspiration index (SPEI index) using 9-month rainfall and temperature. Then using bivariate statistics to combine this drought index with heatwave temperature, to produce climate attribution statements for the compound hazard. This will be carried out using local/regional observational data sets and extended to large climate model ensembles for both factual and counterfactual runs. The second approach is more impact-based and uses a hydrological model to produce river discharge using rainfall and temperature data over the catchment of interest to examine drought. We also aim to extend this to examine mortality from heatwaves using heat-mortality models. This second approach will use local or regional observation datasets and regional climate model data.

Figure 2-3: Workflow for compound heatwave and drought events

2.2.5. Hazards from the demonstrator

The online demonstrator integrates data, models and scripts, such that event-based climate attribution could be showcased on-the-fly. It is realized by investigation of spatiotemporal patterns of compound and cascading hazards using historical data for dry hazards, such as droughts and heatwaves.

The workflow for identifying heatwaves and droughts hazard is shown in Figure 2-4. It begins with the collection of input data from the ERA5-Land dataset. The 2-meter air temperature serves as the primary variable for identifying heatwaves, while the surface solar radiation downwards impacts surface temperature and, consequently, the intensity of heatwaves. Additionally, the 2-meter dewpoint temperature is used as a key indicator of air humidity, which is essential for evaluating drought conditions and the intensity of heatwaves. Total precipitation is monitored to assess drought conditions, as it is a critical factor in determining the availability of water resources. Finally the 10-meter U and V components of wind, which represent the eastward and northward wind speed components at a height of 10 meters can be used for assessing the horizontal transport of heat and moisture, factors that can significantly influence the development of heatwaves and droughts.

Once these input data are collected, they undergo processing to generate several derived variables that further aid in the analysis. Relative humidity is calculated using the air temperature and dewpoint temperature. Total precipitation and the amount of solar radiation reaching the surface are also considered. The surface wind speed is derived from the vector sum of the 10m wind components, providing a comprehensive view of wind conditions. The air temperature is directly used, and two additional variables—temperature range, which represents the difference between maximum and minimum temperatures over a given period, and temperature skewness, which indicates whether the temperature distribution is symmetrical or skewed towards extremes—are calculated to enhance the analysis of heatwaves.

Figure 2-4: Workflow for the droughts and heatwaves impact modelling for the demonstrator

The results of this process yield two primary output variables: the Heatwave Index and the Drought Index. The Heatwave Index is derived from the variables the air temperature variables providing a measure of the intensity and duration of heatwaves. On the other hand, the Drought Index is calculated using the total precipitation, relative humidity, and the amount of solar radiation reaching the surface, offering insights into the intensity and extent of drought conditions. These indices allow for the early detection and monitoring of extreme weather events, facilitating timely and effective responses to mitigate their impacts. In order to ensure on the fly work of the demonstrator the quantitative methods to assess compound extremes of heatwaves and droughts are mainly based on a simple percentile-based peaks-over-threshold methodology.

2.3. Uncertainties and points of attention

Many uncertainties can propagate to impact hazard output variables. Some uncertainties can result from the uncertainties in datasets themselves, as discussed further in section 3.3. Other uncertainties stem from the selected model schematization. For example, the omission of the modelling of important processes or of interactions between hazard drivers can influence hazard output. A common example are dynamic interactions between pluvial, fluvial and coastal drivers for determining flood hazard in coastal areas. Having a compound flood model that resolves the interactions between these three flood drivers is necessary to capture flood extent and observed flood depth. Many studies have shown that these interactions are highly non-linear and therefore cannot be assembled from the output of three separate models (a pluvial model, a coastal model and a fluvial model) but instead require a model schematization that accounts for these dynamics (Bilskie & Hagen, 2018; Santiago-Collazo et al., 2019).

More generally, when applying these workflows or adapting them for the modelling of a specific compound extreme, the following recommendations apply:

- Validation of the model, provided that observational data is available, is of utmost importance to document the model performance and understand the propagation of uncertainties.
- For physics-based models, the resolution of the model schematization (horizontal resolution) should be high enough to ensure numerical stability and convergence. On the other hand, a (too) fine resolution leads to large computation time which can become very limiting if many runs as needed, as can be expected for an attribution study.
- Additionally, for physics-based model, the time step of the model informs of processes that needs to be resolved. Typically, including small-scale features require a finer time step than large-scale one. For example, modelling fluvial flood waves for small catchment typically require an hourly time step whereas for large catchment, a daily time step may be sufficient.
- Global models and datasets do not have the temporal and spatial resolution needed to properly resolve the impact of compound events. Downscaling is needed to achieve reasonable accuracy for these events. We present workflows that employ either dynamical downscaling, using model-based refinements, and statistical downscaling to increase the climate resolution up to an acceptable level. Note that both dynamical and statistical downscaling can be combined, as further discussed in section 4.
- Hazard modelling is often setup using constant parameters linked to exposure and vulnerability, i.e. assuming that exposure and vulnerability do not change in time. For example, flooding extent and depths from a flood event can be quite different for the same catchment with changes in the land cover. Urbanization will result in higher flood peaks and flood volumes but also change the timing of the flood peak. Similarly, topography and bathymetry datasets are often assumed to be static, therefore representing hazard at a specific given moment in time.
- More generally, running the workflow should remain computationally feasible so that an attribution statement can be performed. If the runtime of the workflow is problematic, some simplifications could be applied, and further documented in the uncertainty analysis.

3. From climate to hazard: state-of-the-art datasets

An overview of state-of-the-art large-scale input datasets used for the modelling chains described in Section 2 is given. This includes relevant climate datasets that can be used either to model the observed event or alternative realization of this event (section 3.1), but also general static datasets used for the modelling of specific hazards at continental to global scales (section 3.2). The reader is referred to the COMPASS deliverable 2.1 *“Report on dataset on best-available methods and climate datasets”* for specific details on best-available data and methods that can be used for climate attribution studies and weather types.

3.1. Climate dataset categories for attribution studies

When selecting relevant climate datasets for compound hazard modelling, it is useful to consider the type of desired attribution method and thus requirements for the datasets to construct both the factual, the observed event that serves as a baseline for the analysis, and the counterfactuals, a series of alternative realizations of the observed event, e.g., in a world without climate change (Stott et al., 2016). Hazard modelling for the factual and counterfactual events can stem from the following three broad categories of climate datasets:

Observation-based datasets from gauges and stations or reanalysis datasets. Reanalysis climate data is combined with observations and gap-filled by combining them with historical data from short-range weather forecast models to provide a gridded dataset. In climate science, these datasets are the closest to the “ground truth” for a global scale analysis. Counterfactuals can be generated by removing temporal trend, or after regressing out the change based on another covariate, for e.g. global mean temperature. The temporal coverage of the data should be long enough to include records with low human influence. Usually a counterfactual period

of 30 years, usually 1950 – 1979, to account for natural variability is used to represent observational-based counterfactuals without climate change (Faranda et al., 2022).

Climate model-based datasets from fully coupled climate models to only sea surface temperature-forced model. Climate models can be global or region specific but cover larger timescales than reanalysis datasets from preindustrial times to future projections (generally ~1850-2100). Two ways to generate robust counterfactuals are using a large ensemble of simulations with multiple climate models (at least > 6 models; Hermans et al. (2024)) or using a Single Model Initial-condition Large Ensemble (SMILE; Bevacqua et al. (2023)) consisting of multiple simulations with the same climate model but with different initial states, or both.

Forecast-based datasets from numerical weather prediction (NWP) models, or forecast models. They process current weather to predict future weather at in the short future (upcoming hours to days). These estimates are updated, usually every 6 to 12 hours, and often do not need bias correction unlike climate model based datasets. The main advantage of a NWP model over a climate model is that, they can capture both the important physical processes and their external influence that lead to the event. This is of course provided that the model itself is reliable for the extreme considered. Counterfactuals can then be created by perturbing the initial and boundary conditions of the model. Additionally, ensemble boosting methods can be used to explore plausible alternative realisations of events, potentially with higher intensity (Gessner et al., 2023). Forecast data have shorter timescales but are known to resolve extreme events well due to their high spatial and short-term temporal resolution while account well for natural variability.

This section provides an overview of the most commonly used large scale gridded climate datasets, distinguishing between reanalysis data (3.1.1), modelled climate data (3.1.2) and forecast climate data (3.1.3). Depending on the type of hazard modelling and attribution method, datasets can be selected based on spatial and temporal coverage and resolution and covered climate variables. We do not provide an exhaustive list of climate datasets but rather highlight the most important categories and large-scale datasets commonly used in compound event modelling.

3.1.1. Reanalysis climate data

Multiple institutions and organization have developed gridded reanalysis datasets where they combine observations with modelled data to obtain a consistent product, which can be global or region specific. The most commonly used reanalysis dataset is ERA5(-Land) developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).

Table 3-1: Global or continental gridded reanalysis climate data sources commonly used for hazard modelling

Dataset	Details
Global	
ERA5	The ECMWF Reanalysis v5 (ERA5) datasets is the state-of-the-art gridded atmospheric reanalysis, which is complete and consistent across the globe and covers most atmospheric, ocean-wave and land-surface variables. Spatial resolution: 0.25° (and 0.5° for ocean-waves), vertical resolution of 137 levels Temporal coverage: 1940 – present, hourly (updated daily)
ERA5-Land	The ECMWF Reanalysis v5 - Land (ERA5-Land) is a gridded reanalysis dataset, covering hydrological and biospheric land variables. Spatial resolution: 0.1°, vertical coverage from 2 m above the surface level, to a soil depth of 289 cm divided in 4 levels Temporal coverage: 1950 – present, hourly (updated monthly with a delay of about three months).
FNL	The NCEP FNL (Final) Operational Global Analysis data is a gridded reanalysis dataset based on the GFS forecast data, combined with other observational data sources using NSF NCAR's Global Data Assimilation System (GDAS), covering several atmospheric, oceanic, and land-surface variables. Spatial resolution: 1°, vertical resolution of 26 layers

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	Temporal coverage: 1999 – present, 6-hourly
NCEP-NCAR	The National Centers for Environmental Prediction and the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCEP-NCAR) Reanalysis-1 is a gridded reanalysis dataset, covering a wide range of atmospheric variables. Spatial resolution: 2.5°, vertical resolution of 17 levels Temporal coverage: 1948 – present, 6-hourly
MERRA-2	The Modern-Era Retrospective analysis for Research and Applications, Version 2 (MERRA-2) is a reanalysis dataset developed by NASA, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land surface variables. Spatial resolution: 0.5° x 0.625°, vertical resolution of 72 levels Temporal resolution: 1980 – present, hourly
JRA-55	The Japanese 55-year Reanalysis (JRA-55) is a gridded reanalysis dataset, covering atmospheric and land surface variables. Spatial resolution: 1.25°, vertical resolution of 60 levels Temporal resolution: 1958 – 2024, 3- to 6-hourly
20CRv3	The NOAA/CIRES/DOE 20th Century Reanalysis version 3 (20CRv3) is a gridded reanalysis dataset covering mainly atmospheric variables. Spatial resolution: 1°, vertical resolution of 28 levels Temporal resolution: 1836 – 2015, 3-hourly
CFSR	The Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) from National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) is a reanalysis product of a coupled atmosphere-ocean-land surface-sea ice of a forecasting system, covering atmospheric and ocean variables. Spatial resolution: 0.25° to 0.5°, vertical resolution of 40 to 64 levels Temporal resolution: 1979 – 2010, 6-hourly
Region specific	
UERRA	The Uncertainties in Ensembles of Regional ReAnalysis (UERRA) dataset covering Europe combining analysis from the EURRA-HARMONIE and MESCAN-SURFEX systems, and covering surface and near-surface essential climate variables. Spatial resolution: 5.5 – 11.1 km, single vertical level Temporal resolution: 1961 – 2019, 6-hourly
CERRA	The Copernicus European Regional ReAnalysis (CERRA) dataset aims to produce and deliver a regional reanalysis (RRA) for Europe forced with ERA5, adding in-situ observations and satellite information, and covers surface and near-surface essential climate variables. There is also a specific CERRA-Land dataset including high density surface observations. Another complementary dataset covering the uncertainty of all output parameters is from an Ensemble of Data Assimilation is CERRA-EDA. Spatial resolution: 5.5 – 11.1 km, single vertical level Temporal resolution: 1984 – 2021, 3- to 6-hourly (new data added by the end of 2024)
CHIRPS	The Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Station data (CHIRPS) is a 35+ year quasi-global gridded rainfall data set, covering 50°S-50°N (and all longitudes). The dataset is based on rain gauge data and satellite observations. Spatial resolution: 0.05°, single vertical level Temporal resolution: 1981 – present, daily
JCR MARS	The JRC MARS Meteorological Database is a dataset covering Europe and based on observations from weather stations and developed for agricultural studies, covering atmospheric and vegetation related (e.g., potential evaporation from crop canopy) variables. Spatial resolution: 25 km Temporal resolution: 1979 – 2023, daily

3.1.2. Modelled climate data

Modelled climate data is used here as a broad term for continuous long-term simulated climate data for multiple decades to centuries. There are many climate models available, simulating multiple scenarios with different initial conditions, leading to a lot of different datasets. The Climate Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) is the

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state-of-the-art model intercomparison and is currently in its seventh cycle. Here, some of the most known global and regional climate model datasets are presented but does not include a complete overview.

Table 3-2: Global or continental gridded climate data sources commonly used for hazard modelling

Dataset	Details
Modelled climate data	
CMIP5 , CMIP6 and CMIP7	The Climate Model Intercomparison version 5 (CMIP5) and version 6 (CMIP6) are state-of-the-art multimodel ensembles (version 7 (CMIP7) is currently being developed) providing projections of historical periods and future climate change under different scenarios of greenhouse gas emissions, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land surface variables. Spatial resolution: from 0.125° to 5°, single pressure levels (1 - 1000 hPa) Temporal resolution: 1850 – 2100 (CMIP6), 1850 – 2300 (CMIP5, daily)
SMILEs	A single model initial-condition large ensemble (SMILE) are datasets of a single global or regional climate model (GCM/RCM) run with a range of initial conditions to capture the natural variability of a system separate from external forcings. These runs are also included in CMIP. These ensembles enable a more accurate estimation of the probability distribution, including extreme values. Spatial resolution: from 0.7° to 2.8° Temporal resolution: 1850 – 2100 (varies per SMILE)
CORDEX	The Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) dataset provides high-resolution regional climate simulation for 14 regions across the globe, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land surface variables, depending on the domain. The highest resolution data is available for the Europe domain. Spatial resolution: 0.44° up to 0.11° Temporal resolution: 1950 to 2100, 3-hourly to daily
ISIMIP	The Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP) are bias-adjusted climate datasets, and is based on CMIP data. ISIMIP also provides socioeconomic data, static geographic data and detrended, counterfactual climate datasets. Spatial resolution: 0.5° Temporal resolution: varies per dataset
PRIMAVERA	The Process-based climate simulation: Advances in high-resolution modeling and European climate risk assessments high-resolution climate datasets consists of data from both atmosphere-only and coupled climate runs, covering atmospheric and oceanic variables. The models are also integrated in CMIP6. Spatial resolution: 25 km Temporal resolution: 1950 to 2050, extended to 2100 in the future
ATTRICI	The ATTRibuting Climate Impacts (ATTRICI) is a counterfactual climate dataset for impact attribution and used in ISIMIP, covering atmospheric and land-surface variables. Spatial resolution: 0.5° Temporal resolution: 1901 - 2019, daily
HighResMIP	The High Resolution Model Intercomparison Project (HighResMIP) is a SST-forced model ensemble, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land-surface variables. The model ensemble is also incorporated in CMIP6 Spatial resolution: 25-50 km Temporal resolution: 1950 - 2050
DestinE	The Destination Earth initiative (DestinE) so far has developed two global datasets from Earth Digital Twins, spanning both historic and future times. The datasets are Digital Twins for Climate Change Adaptation and for forecast for Weather-induced and Geophysical Extremes, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land-surface variables. Spatial resolution: 500 m to 50 km, multiple vertical levels Temporal resolution: 1990 – 2040, 5 min to daily
Region specific	
H2020 EUCP	The Horizon2020 European Climate Prediction System (H2020 EUCP) project has developed a high resolution European dataset resulting from Convection Permitting Model (CPM) simulations, covering temperature and precipitation anomalies. The data is separated into multiple domains within Europe. Spatial resolution: 2.2 – 3 km Temporal resolution: 1995 – 2060

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UKCP	The UK Climate Projections (UKCP) data is a United Kingdom (UK) high resolution dataset, although also having data for the whole globe on a lower resolution, covering atmospheric and some hydrological variables. Spatial resolution: 2.2 km (local), 12 km (regional) and 60 km (global) Temporal resolution: 1900 – 2100, hourly to daily
CP4A-Present/-Future	The Convection-Permitting Climate for Africa (CP4A) datasets (Present and Future) are based on high resolution convection permitting climate simulations is, covering atmospheric variables. Spatial resolution: 4.5 km Temporal resolution: 1997-2007 (<i>Present</i> dataset), 2095-2105 (<i>Future</i> dataset)

3.1.3. Forecast data

Forecast data takes place on weather timescales and is developed in an iterative manner using model ensembles. When future climate data extends weather time scales, it is referred to as climate projections which can span multiple decades. Usually, historical forecast data is reused for reanalysis datasets. Generally, forecast data closer to present time are more accurate than further in the future, which is also related to higher temporal resolutions in the near- compared to the far-future.

Table 3-3: Global or continental gridded forecast data sources commonly used for hazard modelling

Forecast data	
GFS	The NCEP GFS 0.25 Degree Global Forecast Grids Historical Archive is, as the name suggests, a gridded global forecast dataset covering several atmospheric, oceanic, and land-surface variables. Spatial resolution: 13km to 0.25°, 26 vertical layers Temporal resolution: 15/01/2015 to present+16 days, 3- to 12-hourly (updated daily)
IFS	A subset of the Integrated Forecast System (IFS) global data by ECMWF is publicly available 1 hour after real-time dissemination and consists of multiple datasets with different resolutions, covering atmospheric, oceanic and land-surface variables. The IFS data is used for the ERA5 reanalysis dataset. Recently, also datasets from Artificial Intelligence Forecasting System (AIFS) are made available. Spatial resolution: 0.25°, 13 vertical layers Temporal resolution: present+10 days, 3- to 6-hourly
TIGGE	The THORPEX Interactive Grand Global Ensemble (TIGGE) is an ensemble forecast dataset from ECMWF, specifically covering (extra-/sub-)tropical cyclone tracks. 6-hourly from 2006 to present, providing up to 32-day forecasts. Spatial resolution: 0.5° to 1.5° Temporal resolution: 2006 - present+32 days, 6-hourly

3.2. Static datasets

Depending on the hazard and the modelling approach considered, additional datasets may be needed. For physics-based models, water-related hazards typically require come further information on land, soils and/or hydrography.

3.2.1. Land cover and soil data

Table 3-4: Global or continental gridded land cover and soil data sources commonly used for hazard modelling

Product	Description
Land use	
Copernicus Global Land Cover	This is a global dataset with 23 land cover classes. Available annually for 2015-2019. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 100 m <u>Spatial coverage:</u> Global
C3S Land Cover	This is a global dataset with 22 land cover classes. Available annually for 1992-2022.

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	<u>Raster resolution:</u> 300 m <u>Spatial coverage:</u> Global
GlobCover	GlobCover contains global coverage of land use, categorized in 22 classes. Maps were produced in 2010. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 300 m <u>Spatial coverage:</u> Global
ESA Worldcover	WorldCover provides the first global land cover products for 2020 and 2021, developed and validated in near-real time based on Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 10 m <u>Spatial coverage:</u> Global
CORINE Land Cover	The CORINE Land Cover (CLC) inventory was initiated in 1985 (reference year 1990). Updates have been produced in 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018. It consists of an inventory of land cover in 44 classes. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 100 m <u>Spatial coverage:</u> Europe
Soil properties	
GCN250	The GCN250 is a globally consistent, gridded dataset defining curve numbers from new global land cover and soil data (Jaafar et al., 2019) for rainfall-runoff modelling. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 250 m <u>Spatial coverage:</u> Global
SoilGrids	SoilGrids is a system for global digital soil mapping that uses state-of-the-art machine learning methods to map the spatial distribution of soil properties across the globe. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 250 m <u>Spatial coverage:</u> Global

3.2.2. Elevation and hydrography data

Accurate information on topography and hydrography is essential for modelling of hydrological hazards such as floods and droughts, as it allows to model how water will flow across a certain location. In riverine flooding, a description of the floodplain and river channel is key to model how overland water will flow across the land. In coastal flood modelling also data on bathymetry is of importance, as it affects how waves will propagate to the coast. In this section we explore which datasets are available for hydrological and flood modelling.

In the modelling of flood hazards topography is commonly represented by using a DEM, digital elevation model, which is a dataset containing the basic representation of the Earth's surface elevation data. It represents the bare-earth surface excluding surface objects such as buildings and trees (the selection of objects that are removed varies per dataset). Some DEMs are accompanied with derived hydrography datasets, i.e. flow directions, channel width and other hydrological parameters.

Available high-quality elevation and hydrography datasets with global or pan-European coverage are listed in Table 3-5. To date, the best global product is FABDEM which is based on the Copernicus DEM but excludes buildings and vegetation. Whenever possible, it is advisable to increase the accuracy of the elevation data by complementing global products with local high-resolution LiDAR (laser altimeter) measurements.

Different DEM datasets will have different accuracy depending on the region and elevation (Uuemaa et al., 2020), which is related to the different source data and methodologies employed in creating them. Vertical accuracy of global DEM datasets can sometimes be in the order of 1-2 meters, but for inland flood modelling the most important factor is the relative accuracy, i.e. whether elevation differences relative to each other are well captured. In coastal flood modelling it is important to understand the differences in vertical references and biases of the topography and bathymetry datasets. In urban areas, higher resolution datasets that can represent urban topography are needed to accurately model flooding, which often requires using local-scale datasets.

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For fluvial flooding, it is important to use hydrography data that is consistent with the elevation data used. For example, MERIT-Hydro, based on MERIT DEM, is frequently used as hydrography and elevation data for riverine flooding.

Table 3-5 Topography and hydrography datasets for hydrological or coastal modelling

Product	Description
Global topography / DEM	
MERIT DEM	MERIT DEM represents high-resolution terrain elevation at a global scale (Yamazaki et al., 2017). This dataset has some features (e.g. forests) removed (buildings not removed). <u>Raster resolution:</u> 3 arc-seconds (about 90 m at equator) <u>Spatial coverage:</u> global
Copernicus DEM	Global and European DEM, containing Earth surface including buildings, infrastructure and vegetation. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 1 arc-second (about 30 m) globally; 10 m in Europe. <u>Spatial coverage:</u> global
FABDEM / FABDEM+	FABDEM dataset is based on Copernicus DEM, with forests and buildings removed (Hawker et al., 2022). FABDEM+ is an improved version of this dataset, that incorporates recent LiDAR data. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 1 arc-second (about 30 m) <u>Spatial coverage:</u> global
NASADEM	Global DEM based on reprocessing of the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) data (Buckley et al., 2020). This is a surface model including buildings and vegetation. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 1 arc-second (about 30 m) <u>Spatial coverage:</u> global
DeltaDTM	A global coastal digital terrain model, based on Copernicus DEM, designed for improved accuracy in low-lying coastal areas (currently below 10m MSL) (Pronk et al., 2024). <u>Raster resolution:</u> 1 arc-second (about 30 m) <u>Spatial coverage:</u> global
Hydrography	
MERIT Hydro	MERIT Hydro is a global hydrography raster dataset, developed based on the MERIT DEM and multiple inland water maps. It contains flow direction, flow accumulation, hydrologically adjusted elevations, river channel width, upstream drainage area and height above nearest drainage. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 3 arc-seconds (about 90 m) <u>Spatial coverage:</u> global
EU-Hydro	EU-Hydro is a pan-European dataset that includes a photo-interpreted river network consistent with surface interpretation of water bodies (lakes and wide rivers) as well as a drainage model (CLMS, 2020). <u>Vector dataset</u> <u>Spatial coverage:</u> Europe (EEA countries and UK).
HydroSHEDS	HydroSHEDS consists of several hydrographic data products including hydrologically-conditioned DEM, catchment boundaries, river networks, and lakes. The various existing sub-datasets are consistent across multiple scales and resolutions in order to support regional and global hydro-environmental modelling (Lehner et al., 2008). Contains raster maps of flow directions, flow accumulation, polygons of catchments, rivers, lakes. <u>Raster resolution:</u> 3 arc-seconds (90 m). <u>Vector datasets</u> with water body and catchment polygons. <u>Spatial coverage:</u> global.
Bathymetry	

GEBCO	<p>Global terrain model for ocean and land, providing elevation data (IOC, IHO and BODC, 2003).</p> <p><u>Raster resolution:</u> 15 arc-seconds (about 265 m) <u>Spatial coverage:</u> global.</p>
EMODnet Digital Bathymetry	<p>Bathymetric product based on a harmonized Digital Terrain Model (DTM) for the European sea regions.</p> <p><u>Raster resolution:</u> 115 m. <u>Spatial coverage:</u> Europe.</p>

3.3. Uncertainties and points of attention

Uncertainties in the compound hazard modelling are also introduced from the selection of the datasets. Large scale climate datasets typically have a spatial resolution between 0.25 and 2.5 degree. While computational power is increasing and the new generation of climate datasets always aims to improve this spatial resolution, the current spatial resolution remains too coarse to resolve small-scale processes of importance to capture extremes. For example, tropical cyclones remain poorly resolved in reanalysis datasets. Nevertheless, using these datasets not only allow for having globally-applicable framework, it is also often closely related to the type of attribution study to be performed. A sensitivity analysis is required to document uncertainties introduced by the selection of the dataset.

4. Specific requirements for COMPASS Use Cases

This section details specific technical requirements for each Use Case (UC) defined in Phase I of the project. For each UC, we provide further information on the choices of specific (global or local) datasets that will be used in the hazard modelling, and on which models are going to be used to model the components of the hazard. This overview builds upon the modelling schematizations presented in Section 2.

4.1. UC 1 – Extra-tropical Storm Xynthia

Extreme sea levels were derived from several datasets. The principal component of extreme sea levels are storm surge heights, which were estimated through a continuous simulation in Delft3D. This hydrodynamic model is commonly applied in continental- or global-scale surge modelling (e.g. Muis et al., 2020; Vousdoukas et al., 2016). The model set-up is the same as described in Paprotny et al., (2016, 2019), with the difference that it was recalibrated to adapt it to a new forcing dataset (ERA5). The model was run from 1 January 1949 to 31 December 2020, with the first year used only as spin-up. Forcing is by wind (u and v components) and surface pressure. Significant wave heights were also taken from ERA5. Tidal elevations were computed with pyTMD package (<https://github.com/tsutterley/pyTMD>) from 34 tidal constituents from FES2014 (Lyard et al., 2021). Mean dynamic topography defined as the average sea surface height for 1993–2012 above geoid and taken from the Global Ocean Mean Dynamic Topography (Mulet et al., 2021). Long-term SLR was added from several datasets, HCC by Treu et al. (2024) for 1950-1999, European Seas Gridded L4 Sea Surface Heights from 2000-2020 (Taburet et al., 2019), with coarser Global Ocean Gridded L4 Sea Surface Heights also used for gap-filling data in northernmost parts of Europe (Pujol et al., 2016). Finally, GIA was added from ICE-6G_C model (Argus et al., 2014; Peltier et al., 2015).

Coastal inundation modelling was carried out according to a methodology developed by Vousdoukas et al. (2016). Briefly, the maps were generated with the Lisflood-ACC (LFP) model (Bates et al., 2010) applied at 30 m spatial resolution. In terms of Digital Elevation Model (DEM), we use the recently published DeltaDEM (Pronk et al., 2024) after applying post-processing using global LIDAR observations to further remove vertical bias, correcting for buildings and vegetation. The simulations consider gridded hydraulic roughness values derived from land-use maps (Zanaga et al., 2022). Lisflood-ACC is applied for each coastal segment with the model domain extending up to 200 km landwards in order to ensure the inclusion of all potentially hydrologically

connected areas that may lie inland and away from the coast. However, possibilities of high-resolution local inundation modelling will be explored with local collaborators, particularly La Rochelle University.

Hourly wind speeds (u and v component converted into a single vector) will be derived from ERA5-Land reanalysis at 0.1° resolution. It will enable detection, detrending and attribution of windstorm damage across France. An alternative approach will be analysed, using daily wind speed with downscaling and bias-adjustment, which could also be more easily used to create counterfactual data with ATTRICI method. However, the importance of high temporal resolution likely will be greater than of higher spatial resolution.

4.2. UC 2a – Winter storms of 2013/14

In UC 2a we are focusing on modelling compound flooding as a result of the multi-variate compound hazards associated with the storm season of 2013/14, when Ireland and the UK experienced unprecedented rainfall and significant storms surges (Matthews et al., 2014; Met Office, 2014).

The modelling chain for this UC is based on that presented in Figure 4-1. A description of the model and the input datasets to be initially used is given next, in section 4.4. For the topography data, the [LIDAR composite digital terrain model](#) will be used which has a spatial resolution of 1 km. Coastal boundary conditions will be extracted from the [GESLA](#) datasets, provided that they cover the area of interest and have reliable observations for the events.

4.3. UC 2b – Heatwaves and droughts of summer 2022

The modelling chain for this UC is shown in Figure 2-3:

- Approach 1 uses a statistical approach where hazard modelling is not required.
- Approach 2 for this UC uses wflow hydrological model, examining low flows rather than high flows, see section 4.4.

4.4. UC 3a – Tropical Cyclones Idai, Kenneth and Freddy

In UC3a we are focusing on modelling compound flooding due to tropical cyclones focusing specifically on the coastal areas in Mozambique affected by the tropical cyclones (TCs) Idai (March 2019), Kenneth (April 2019) and Freddy (February 2023). For the TC Idai and TC Kenneth, we aim to also investigate the sequential nature of the cyclones and its effect on flooding.

The modelling chain for this use case is presented in Figure 4-1 (based on the modelling chain presented in Section 2, see Figure 2-2). Hazard models in this workflow are open-source models that have already been extensively used for the purpose of compound flood modelling.

Figure 4-1 Modelling chain for compound flood hazard under tropical cyclones (Use Case 3a).

Compound flood model

Compound flood modelling will be done using the **SFINCS (Super-Fast INundation of Coasts) model**. SFINCS is a reduced-complexity model capable of simulating compound flooding with a high computational efficiency balanced with an adequate accuracy. In SFINCS a set of momentum and continuity equations are solved with a first order explicit scheme based on Bates et al. (2010). Traditionally SFINCS neglects the advection term (SFINCS-LIE) which is generally justified for sub-critical flow conditions. For supercritical flow conditions or when modelling waves, the advection term needs to be solved. For this purpose, the SFINCS-SSWE version can be used (including advection). For more information see Leijnse et al. (2021).

SFINCS balances a high computational efficiency with good accuracy and is therefore perfectly equipped for compound flooding in operational forecasting systems. To simulate compound flooding events, a model needs to be able to use all relevant forcings. Therefore, SFINCS includes fluvial, pluvial, tidal, wind- and wave-driven processes.

SFINCS relies on a number of inputs, the main of which are listed below:

- **Topography and river geometry** based on a global elevation dataset as well as hydrographic information on river geometry, by default MERIT DEM in combination with MERIT Hydro are used.
- **Bathymetry** data is used as input to the SFINCS model in order to be able to translate the near-shore coastal water level conditions to the coastline and overland. By default GEBCO dataset is used.
- **Land cover** data needed to define spatially varying manning roughness of the land surface, based on a global dataset, by default from Copernicus Global Land Cover. Land surface infiltration is estimated based on the [GCN250](#) dataset of curve numbers derived from global land cover.
- **Precipitation** data can be directly derived from climate datasets with possible pre-processing to better schematize rainfall based on tropical cyclone track data. Statistical downscaling methods could be tested and compared to other options such as using runoff from ERA5 or from a hydrological model.
- **River discharges** are obtained by means of hydrological model (wflow, see below).
- **Coastal water levels** are a combination of tide, storm surge and wave set-up, where the latter two are closely linked to the meteorological conditions during the tropical cyclone. These water levels are obtained by means of local hydrodynamic and wave models. Surge levels can be calculated using a local

Delft3D-FM model implementation or an offshore extension of SFINCS, while wave setup is obtained from larger scale wave modelling (at basin level) and local nearshore wave modelling to compute wave set-up.

Spatial **boundaries** of a SFINCS model are defined based on watershed boundaries (inland boundary) and maximum nearshore water depth (ocean boundary). At the inland boundary, river discharges are specified at river inflow points. At the coastal boundary, coastal water levels are specified along the boundary. When available, river discharge and coastal water levels can be used from observations, for example using the [GRDC](#) dataset or the [GESLA](#) dataset, respectively. However, those datasets do not cover data poor areas like Mozambique or they do not contain recent data.

As **output** from the overland SFINCS model we can obtain spatially and temporally varying flood inundation maps, as well as water levels at pre-defined observation points.

It is also possible to use SFINCS to create an offshore model (extending to deeper waters) and use it to compute nearshore water levels without the need for a different hydrodynamic model. This option is described in more detail in the respective section below.

Hydrological model

Hydrological modelling of river discharges will be done using the **wflow model**¹. wflow models hydrological processes, allowing users to account for precipitation, interception, snow accumulation and melt, evapotranspiration, soil water, surface water and groundwater recharge. Based on gridded topography, soil, land use and climate data, wflow calculates all hydrological fluxes at any given grid cell in the model at a given time step. Wflow has been successfully applied worldwide for analyzing flood hazards, drought, climate change impacts and land use changes. Wflow is conceived as a framework, within which multiple distributed model concepts are available, which maximizes the use of open earth observation data, making it the hydrological model of choice for data scarce environments.

Wflow is a free and open source distributed hydrological model developed to predict discharge volumes and levels by maximum usage of earth observations and additional high-resolution data. Models can be set up (automated) for river basins around the globe using open data at various spatial resolutions, using the open source wflow plugin of the HydroMT python package developed by Deltares available from Zenodo (Eilander et al., 2021; van Verseveld et al., 2024). The model parameters are estimated from point-scale pedotransfer functions (Imhoff et al., 2020) that relate the model's parameter values to physical system characteristics such as soil type, soil conductivity, etc. From the wflow simulations we obtain the simulated discharges of the rivers that enter the SFINCS model grid and the effective precipitation.

Wflow relies on a number of inputs:

- **Topography and hydrography** based on a global elevation and hydrography dataset, by default MERIT-Hydro is used. Next to that, the river lines dataset of Lin et al. (2019) is used to derive the river width and bank full capacity for each river cell in the model.
- **Land cover** data needed to define spatially varying manning roughness of the land surface, based on a global dataset, by default from Copernicus Global Land Cover. Next to the static land use map, wflow can also use dynamic vegetation cover as input in the form of Leaf Area Index (LAI) data. LAI data is taken from MODIS and provides a monthly changing vegetation cover, which is used in the calculation of interception and transpiration through the plants.

¹ <https://deltares.github.io/wflow.jl/stable/>

- **Soil type information** is based on the the SoilGrids250m dataset (Hengl et al., 2017) is used. SoilGrids v1 250m provides estimates of soil properties at several depth intervals at a spatial resolution of 250x250 meter globally. The soil properties are very relevant for the hydrological response since they largely determine the generation of runoff from rainfall.
- **Meteorological forcing (precipitation, temperature)** data can be directly derived from climate datasets with possible pre-processing to better schematise rainfall based on tropical cyclone track data.

Spatial boundaries of the wflow model are determined based on the wider watershed boundaries that are deemed relevant to the river discharges during the extreme event.

Coastal hydrodynamic model

A coastal hydrodynamic model is necessary in order to accurately estimate the coastal storm surge levels generated during the tropical cyclone. For this purpose, we will use the **Delft3D Flexible Mesh (FM) model**². We will model the tides and storm surges using depth-averaged hydrodynamics (2D). A regional model can be set up using the open-source package *dfm_tools*³ with appropriate resolution and geographical extent. The geographical extent should be sufficient to fully include the surge generated by the tropical cyclone.

An alternative simplified hydrodynamic model can be setup using SFINCS with an extension towards offshore. This is a simplified hydrodynamic model that is more computationally efficient and optimal for performing large ensembles of computations. The accuracy of this model for the purposes of tropical cyclone surge modelling will be assessed before selecting the hydrodynamic model.

The hydrodynamic model relies on a number of inputs, the main of which are listed below:

- **Bathymetry** data is important as it affects both tidal and surge levels. By default GEBCO dataset is used.
- **Meteorological forcing** (wind speeds and mean sea level atmospheric pressure) needs to be defined to model surge generation. The forcing should adequately represent the meteorological conditions during a tropical cyclone.
- **Tidal conditions** are prescribed along the offshore boundary of the coastal model. These can be derived from global databases such as FES⁴, TPXO⁵ or GTSM⁶.

Wave model

To account for wave setup, various models can be used, and a combination of models can be necessary to arrive to accurate estimation of wave setup. A regional wave model for wave generation in deep water can be set up using **HurryWave** – a wave model developed by Deltares to simulate the generation and propagation of sea-swell waves by wind forcing. A third-generation spectral wave model similar to [SWAN](#) or [WAVEWATCH-III](#), HurryWave is, on average, an order of magnitude faster than the SWAN model due to its very slightly reduced physics, combined with simpler wave propagation schemes.

² <https://www.deltares.nl/en/software-and-data/products/delft3d-flexible-mesh-suite>

³ https://github.com/Deltares/dfm_tools

⁴ <https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/en/data/products/auxiliary-products/global-tide-fes/release-fes22.html>

⁵ <https://www.tpxo.net/global>

⁶ <https://publicwiki.deltares.nl/display/GTSM/Global+Tide+and+Surge+Model>

The **BEWARE** (Bayesian Estimator of Wave Attack in Reef Environments) model can be used for areas with steep coasts or reefs. This model is based on a synthetic database originally constructed from approximately 100,000 1-Dimensional XBeach simulations, forced with a range of hydrodynamic conditions (Pearson et al., 2017). **XBeach** is an open-source model for simulating wave propagation, long waves, mean flow, sediment transport and morphological changes in the nearshore environment.

The nearshore wave setup can be computed using the **SNAPWAVE** model. This model is developed by Deltares and is used to estimate nearshore wave setup as part of a workflow using the SFINCS flood model.

The extent and complexity of the required wave modelling depends on how exposed the coastline is and on the near-shore bathymetry profile. Within the project we will investigate which wave modelling setup is necessary to optimally model the wave setup component of coastal water levels within reasonable computational resources.

Tropical cyclone data

Since UC3 is focusing on tropical cyclones, the aim is to integrate specific datasets for tropical cyclones that can be of use to either validate or refine the global datasets. For example, IBTrACS provides best-track historical records of tropical cyclones, including their tracks and various key meteorological indicator such as wind speed. This data is more accurate than reanalysis product such as ERA5 that have a lower spatial resolution and thus often underestimates wind extremes. IBTrACS data can be used to create detailed wind profiles along the tropical cyclone track, most often using the Holland wind profile model. IBTrACS does not contain rainfall information. Recent compound flooding studies have used ERA5, a starting point for the modelling here. However, we will be comparing this product with other products such as CHIRPS.

4.5. UC 4 – Tropical cyclones Eta and Iota

In UC4 we are focusing on consecutive tropical cyclones in the Caribbean, specifically Honduras and surrounding countries, using the sequence of tropical cyclones Eta and Iota that caused significant impacts in 2020. UC4 is broadly using a storylines approach to enable the integration of both quantitative hazard, impact, and vulnerability data, and qualitative evidence of impacts and vulnerability.

Hazard modeling will use both ERA5 re-analysis and CHIRPS rainfall to approximate rainfall intensities and wind speeds, along with IBTrACS cyclone track data for further validation. Different counterfactuals will be explored including scaling rainfall intensity according Clausius-Clapeyron relation ($\sim 7\% \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$) and using forecast model ensemble boosting to construct downward counterfactuals. For this we will use the TIGGE forecast archive.

River level modeling will use wflow as described for UC3 above but configured for Honduras and parts surrounding countries. Flood inundation will be modelled either using SFINCS. While only limited gauge data is available for calibration/validation, flood extents will be compared with satellite-based flood extent mapping and integrated with qualitative evidence on flood extent and intensity. This approach will generate important guidance on integrating quantitative and qualitative evidence, particularly in data poor regions.

Coastal and inland inundation modeling will use the SFINCS model described in UC3 above and configured for key parts of coastline of Honduras. While significant impacts were experienced inland, it will still be important to model the coastal impacts.

Health impact modeling will be explored using data driven approaches such as random forest modeling using health observatory data

4.6. UC 5 – Heatwave and Drought

In UC 5, we are modelling heatwaves and droughts for which the variables were taken from ERA5-Land at 0.1° resolution which will be bias-adjusted and downscaled to the finer resolution of EMO-1 data which is 0.0167°

resolution. The following variables will be extracted from the datasets and corresponding to the workflow shown in Figure 2-4: the 2-meter air temperature (*t2m*), the surface solar radiation downwards (*ssrd*), the 2-meter dewpoint temperature (*td2m*), the 10-meter U and V components of wind (*u10* and *v10*), the total precipitation (*tp*), The air temperature (*tas*), temperature range (*tasrange*), temperature skewness (*tasskew*).

By downscaling the data to the higher resolution of 0.0167° (matching the EMO-1 data), the model can capture more detailed spatial patterns and provide more localized and precise impact identification. For this purpose, the **ISIMIP3BASD** model (Lange, 2019) will be utilized. The model uses an advanced quantile mapping method for all climate variables, enabling controlled bias adjustment across all quantiles. This new method better preserves trends compared to the predecessor models and provides more robust bias correction in extreme quantiles due to its parametric nature.

The ISIMIP3BASD model utilizes MBCnSD algorithm which is applied separately to each climate variable and calendar month. It requires that the coarse grid (in our case ERA5-Land) of the climate simulation data and the fine grid (EMO-1) of the observation data are aligned, with each fine grid cell fully contained within a single coarse grid cell. The procedure initially requires both the ERA5-Land and EMO-1 data to be pre-processed into similar format in-order to have no spatial alignment issues, this procedure requires the use of Python scripts based on libraries such as cdo (<https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo/wiki/Libs4cdo>) and nco (<https://nco.sourceforge.net/>).

5. Next steps

This deliverable will be updated through the project for a final version, corresponding to deliverable D1.2. The updated version will provide some additional information on other potential limitations and recommendations for compound extreme hazard modelling based on the outcomes of the modelling for the UC. In the second phase of the project, a new UC will be selected to test one of the hazard modelling workflow described here.

Based on this deliverable, the following generic guidelines for compound extreme hazard modelling can be made:

- Uncertainties in the modelling chain should be assessed and documented. Each component of the suggested workflow have some uncertainties that can propagate to influence the hazard output. Uncertainty propagation can be performed in multiple ways but at minimum a simple sensitivity analysis (i.e. one-at-a-time sensitivity) should be performed. Other methods use bootstrapping methods or multiple climate datasets to help inform on the confidence of the modelling. An extensive review of sensitivity analysis methods and best practices is given in Pianosi et al. (2016).
- The spatial and temporal resolution of large-scale climate datasets may not be sufficiently high to accurately resolve compound events, such as tropical cyclones. In this case, they should be complemented by additional (statistical or dynamical) downscaling.
- Validation of the modeling framework should be performed when possible to guide the uncertainty analysis and provide robustness in the analysis

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